

EFFECT OF GIRTH CLASS ON GUM YIELD OF *Acacia nilotica* (L.) Del. USING V-SHAPED TAPPING TECHNIQUEVaishnavi Madhukar Gawande¹, A. U. Nimkar², S.S. Harne³ and V. B. Shambharkar⁴

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Abstract

Acacia gums are dried exudates sourced from trees belonging to various species within the *Acacia* genus. Scientific tapping techniques enhances gum production. The objective of the experiment was, to study suitable girth class of *Acacia nilotica* using V-shaped tapping technique. Trees of *Acacia nilotica* were selected and marked for tapping from the following five girth classes viz; 60-65 cm, 65-75cm, 75-85cm, 85-95 cm and above 95 cm. At each girth class, eight trees were selected and total forty trees were marked for tapping. Tapping of the trees involved creating two V-shaped blaze and the gum was collected at 15-day intervals. Total twelve gum collections were carried out throughout the experiment. Statistical analysis was conducted using a Randomized Block Design (RBD). Among these girth classes, significantly the highest average gum yield was observed in the G4 treatment, with 37.31 grams. This was significantly higher than G5, which yielded 13.21 grams. G3 followed with 11.33 grams, G2 had 9.50 grams, and the lowest yield was in G1 at 6.26 grams. The gum yield performance of *Acacia nilotica* was ranked as G4 > G5 > G3 > G2 > G1.

Keywords: *Acacia nilotica*, girth class, V-shaped blaze, tapping, gum arabic, freshening's**Introduction**

Acacia nilotica (Babul tree) is one of the major gum-yielding acacia species found in the Indian subcontinent (Bhushette and Annapure 2017). At the end of the rainy season, the stems begin to exude the gum. In about fifteen days it thickens in the furrow down in which it runs. It then hardens on exposure to the air usually in the form of round or oval tears, about the size of a pigeon's egg but sometimes in vermicular forms, white or red, according to whether the species is a white or red gum tree. Thereafter, it is harvested and marketed as 'Gum Arabic'. (Jani *et al.*, 2015). It exudes from bark other naturally or in response to injury. Traditionally trees are tapped by blazing, stripping of the bark making deep cuts with axe, and in this process plant get injured at various points and produce only few quantity of gum due to which gum tappers have no interests in gum tapping (Awouda, 1989; Tadesse *et al.*, 2007; Ram *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, there is an urgent need to standardize scientific tapping techniques in all valuable gum and resin producing trees species to avoid unscientific method of gum tapping. Trees with larger girth have a larger surface area for gum exudation, resulting in a higher potential gum yield. The increment in girth usually signifies a more developed vascular system, allowing for increased gum production. Tapping these trees can yield a greater quantity of gum due to their higher capacity for exudation. Tapping for the production of gum arabic involves removing sections of the bark with a sharp material (e.g. axe) (Girmay and Mulugeta, 2010). Tapping direction play an important role in increasing gum yield. Gum yield was greatly increased by tapping on the eastern and western sides of the tree. The effect of sun light which seems to boost the temperature at the side of the incisions. Sunlight enhances gum arabic exudation process and affects the purity of gum (Adam *et al.*, 2009). Traditional method of gum tapping is crude and unscientific; the deep incision, untimely extraction and high concentration of chemical in gum have affected the *Acacia nilotica* species in its natural habitat. Gum tapping should be done in summer

month i.e. April and May to ensure sustainable supply of gum and good economic growth. (Vasishth, 2017).

Material And Methods

The experiment was carried out at Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola. The natural population of *Acacia nilotica* is mostly occurred in the university campus, so that the trees were kept under systematic observation. The trees having girth ranged from 50-110 cm was selected for tapping. At each girth class, eight trees were selected and total forty trees were marked in for tapping. The selected trees were marked with pink coloured tags and were numbered for identification. Trees of *Acacia nilotica* were selected and marked for tapping from the following five girth classes viz; 60-65 cm, 65-75cm, 75-85cm, 85-95 cm and above 95 cm. To accelerate gum exudation, a V-shaped blaze were made on each marked tree by stripping away the bark using chisel and hammer. The V-shaped blaze were made of 1.25 – 1.50 cm deep and 1 cm wide depending upon the thickness of bark of the *Acacia nilotica* tree. Each arm of V-shaped rill measuring 7.5 cm in length on lower side and 6.5 cm on upper side. The V-shaped blaze were made at east side at a height of 90 cm above ground and second V-shaped blaze were made at west side at a height of 120 cm above ground level. After tapping, the gum starts oozes out from blazes. The gum was collected at 15 days intervals. Total twelve pickings were made during the period of six month.

To avoid clogging of gum in the gum canals and consequently for getting optimum yield of gum, timely and repeated freshening's are essential which were done at the time of collection of gum. Fortnightly freshening's of blaze were undertaken in all the forty tree where tapping was carried out. In each freshening about 2 mm was shaved off from all the sides of V-shaped blaze without increasing the depth of the blaze. The remaining three sides and surface of the blaze were also scrapped off so that the clogged canals could opened up.

Treatment	Girth Class (cm)
G1	60-65
G2	65-75
G3	75-85
G4	85-95
G5	More than 95

Results And Discussion

The result from the experiment shows that range of differences among various girth classes, Table 1 shows the average gum yield categorized by girth class. The G4 treatment stands out with the significantly highest average gum yield at 37.31 grams. Followed by G5 with 13.21 grams, G3 with 11.33 grams, G2 with 9.50 grams, and the lowest yield in G1 at 6.26 grams. The gum yield performance of *Acacia nilotica* is

ranked as G4 > G5 > G3 > G2 > G1, as shown in Figure 2. Pareek *et al.* (2017) reported similar findings and clearly indicating that girth has positively correlation with gum yield. This might be due to the abundance of vascular bundles rich of rays, which are responsible for preserving gum deposits.

Table 1. Girth class wise average performance of gum yield

Treatment	Gum yield (g)	Average gum yield(g)
G1 (60-65 cm)	50.06	6.26
G2 (65-75 cm)	75.97	9.50
G3 (75-85 cm)	90.65	11.33
G4 (85-95 cm)	298.48	37.31
G5 (>95 cm)	95.7	13.21
Mean	122.17	15.52
F-Test (p=0.05)		Sig.
S.E.(m)±		2.36
CD or LSD		6.85

Total Gum yield (g)

Fig 2: Pie chart showing girth classes and gum yield of *Acacia nilotica* during six month duration.

Table 2 displays the relationship between the gum yields of marked trees and the number of pickings. The highest gum yield, at 88.18 grams, was recorded during the sixth picking in the second week of April 2024. This was followed by the fifth picking with a yield of 73.71 grams and the seventh picking at 70.08 grams. Conversely, the lowest yield was observed during the twelfth picking, which recorded 26.42 grams in the second week of July 2024.

Table 2: Gum yield of *Acacia nilotica* tree in relation to number of pickings carried out at University campus Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola.

Treatment	Gum yield (gm)											
	1 st gum picking	2 nd gum picking	3 rd gum picking	4 th gum picking	5 th gum picking	6 th gum picking	7 th gum picking	8 th gum picking	9 th gum picking	10 th gum picking	11 th gum picking	12 th gum picking
G1	3.51	3.40	4.12	4.38	4.76	6.28	5.96	4.36	4.62	3.32	3.21	2.14
G2	4.31	5.29	5.87	7.07	6.57	9.05	6.81	7.20	7.43	6.22	5.92	4.23
G3	5.05	5.23	7.53	8.30	10.13	11.69	8.72	8.14	7.24	6.66	6.38	5.58
G4	10.28	11.34	24.43	36.12	42.22	48.67	37.55	26.57	19.28	17.49	15.32	9.21
G5	6.17	6.29	7.33	8.38	10.03	12.49	11.04	10.21	7.05	5.17	6.28	5.26
Total gum yield	29.32	31.55	49.28	64.25	73.71	88.18	70.08	56.48	45.62	38.86	37.11	26.42
Mean	5.86	6.31	9.86	12.85	14.74	17.64	14.02	11.30	9.12	7.77	7.42	5.28

Graphical representation of gum yield in relation to the number of pickings is displayed in Figure 3. Ballal *et al.* (2005) and Abdalla (2007) indicated that the first and second pickings play a crucial role in gum arabic production and can serve as indicators for predicting the total gum arabic yield. On the other hand Ballal *et al.* (2005) noted that gum arabic production increases from the first pick, peaks during the second pick and then slightly decreases in the third pick, continuing to decline up to the eighth pick. This reduction in gum arabic yield from the first to the second picking may be attributed to the sealing of some

wound areas after the initial pick, which restricts exudation to smaller openings in the wound sites.

In the present study, the decrease in gum yield from the eighth to the twelfth picking may be attributed to the exceptionally high temperatures experienced in Akola from late April to early July. The rapid drying of the tree bark due to intense heat, very hot air, and extremely low humidity makes it challenging for the gum to ooze from the bark or gum canals. This loss of moisture can cause the gum to become more solid and difficult to extract, resulting in reduced production during May and June in Akola. It is noteworthy that gum yield exhibits an increasing

trend with girth class up to a certain threshold (85-95 cm), after which it starts to decline. Similar type of result had been observed by Snehal Shende in 2023.

Fig 3. Relation of girth classes and no. of picking

Conclusions

The highest gum yield was recorded in the G4 girth class (85-95 cm), with most of the top yields falling within this class. Notably, tree D2 yielded 62.48 g, followed by B7 with 45.65 g, and C10 with 42.64 g. It is noteworthy that gum yield exhibits an increasing trend with girth class up to a certain threshold (85-95 cm), after which it starts to decline. *Acacia nilotica* tree having girth class of 85-95 cm is suitable for tapping of gum by keeping V-shaped blaze, 90 cm from east side and 120 cm from west side above the ground level for obtaining maximum gum yield.

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